

MEASUREMENT OF EXCHANGEABLE IONS IN DIFFERENT AFFINITY LEVELS

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The difference in the exchangeability of a particular cation at different degrees of saturation has been demonstrated by allowing the heteroionic systems, $\text{NH}_4 \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Ba} \\ \text{Na} \end{array} \right\}$ -clay and $\text{NH}_4 \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Ba} \\ \text{Na} \end{array} \right\}$ -clay to equilibrate with H-resin in cellophane bags. The existence of 'loosely' and 'firmly' bound conditions of the same cation is clearly noticeable from the experimental data. This confirms the earlier observations of Mukherjee and co-workers using electrolytes for the purpose of exchange.

The same cation is adsorbed by different clay minerals with different bonding energies because of the difference in the lattice forces, but with regard to the same clay mineral also, a particular cation may be adsorbed with different bonding energies. This was suggested by Wiegner and Mitchell (*J. Land.*, 1912, 60, 111, 197) in the case of permutites and extended by Wiegner (*Trans. Int. Cong. Soil Sci.*, 3rd Congr., Oxford, 1935, p. 111), Ganguly and Mukherjee (*J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1951, 55, 1429) and Marshall (*Soil Sci.*, 1948, 66, 57) in the case of clay minerals. Bottini (*Kolloid Z.*, 1937, 78, 68) measured the amount of ammonia evolved from Ca-NH₄-clay and NH₄-Ca-clay by thermal treatment and found in agreement with the earlier observation that the -NH₄⁺ ion was held differently in these two clays. Vanselow (*Soil Sci.*, 1932, 33, 95) with the same mixed clay determined the equilibrium constants and found them to differ, proving that the release of ions depends on the priority of adsorption on the clay surface. The existence of H⁺ ions in definite affinity levels on the surface of clay minerals has been established by the researches of Mukherjee and co-workers (Special publication, I.A.-C.S. Calcutta, No. XIII, 1947), who used electrolytes for purposes of exchange. In the present paper, as noted below, an acid exchanger, separated by a cellophane bag, has been used for the same purpose.

From a close study of the neutralisation curves and salt titrations or exchangeable isotherms of clay acids and salts, it is now well established that the exchangeable ions are not of equal bonding energies (Marshall, "The Colloid Chemistry of Silicate Minerals"; Mitra, *Indian Soc. Soil Sci. Bull.*, 1941-42, 4, 21). Several categories of the same cation, saturating the clay, have been recognised. This also finds support from the crystalline structure of the clay minerals. The nutrient ions present in the soil are supposed to be made available to the plant by means of an exchange process. In that case the availability will be influenced by the exchangeability of the different category of ions of the clays. The exchangeability of the ions is determined by their bonding energy to the clays. Consequently, the cations of the clays with higher bonding energies will exchange for a particular exchanging cation, if the concentration of the latter is gradually increased. In the plant-soil relationship it is assumed that the exchanging cation is hydrogen, which is liberated by the plant roots.

The experimental arrangement that is likely to simulate plant-root fairly closely is to have a more or less solid acid exchanger which may be allowed to equilibrate under proper conditions with the soil or the exchange material present in it, *i.e.*, the colloidal clays. Such an arrangement has been worked out by Brown and Albrecht (Res. Bull. No. 477, College of Agric. Univ. of Mo., 1950). They used a collodion membrane to separate a soil or the clay, saturated with one or more cations, from a desaturated clay of the montmorillonite type having high b.e.c. The amount of the cations extracted by the desaturated clay, which simulated the acidic environment of the plant-roots, was then determined. Brown *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) have established that the different cations in a soil or clay exist in "suites", depending obviously on their respective bonding energies. Working with a homoionic soil or clay, *i.e.*, saturated with one kind of cation, they observed different rates of extraction over, more or less, definite range of saturation.

In this paper, the technique of Brown and Albrecht (*loc. cit.*) was used to observe the difference in exchangeability of some binary clays, which were saturated with different proportions of a pair of cations but having somewhat known exchange characteristics. According to the earlier observations of Renold (Koll. - Chem. Beih., 1936, 43, 1), Wiegner (*loc. cit.*) and Ganguly and Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*), the exchangeability of a cation in presence of another is determined by the manner of its addition. Thus, the cation that is added first is more difficult to exchange than the one added next; so that a binary clay, $\text{NH}_4\text{—Ba}$ clay, is different from a Ba—NH_4 clay, having the same proportion of the cations. The difference is more prominent with regard to exchangeability or properties closely related to it. Ganguly and Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*) have further shown that the difference in exchangeability becomes evident only after a "critical ratio" of the two ions concerned is exceeded. The binary clays containing varying proportions of Ba^{2+} and NH_4^+ and Na^+ and NH_4^+ ions have been prepared in the following manner.

EXPERIMENTAL

To a known amount of H-clay, the calculated amount of one of the bases required to attain a definite extent of saturation was added first in the form of hydroxide and the mixture was allowed to equilibrate. After about a week or more, the other base was similarly added to complete the saturation and allowed to come to equilibrium. In this way, a pair of clays, e.g., Ba—NH_4 -clay and $\text{NH}_4\text{—Ba}$ -clay was obtained. Three different ratios, viz., 70:30, 50:50 and 30:70, were used for the same pair of cations. Usually the cation written next to 'clay', e.g. NH_4^+ in Ba—NH_4 -clay, is purported to be more difficult to exchange than the NH_4^+ written away from 'clay', viz., $\text{NH}_4\text{—Ba}$ -clay. The same is true of Ba^{2+} ions and other pairs of ions.

The clays were then allowed to exchange for H^+ ions of H-resin taken in cellophane bags by immersing them into the clay suspensions. The bottles containing the clays were thoroughly paraffined so as to prevent evaporation of water from the contents of the bottles. The amount of H-resin was so adjusted that it corresponded to the

total amount of bases present in the clay, *i.e.*, in the symmetry concentration. Sufficient time was allowed to attain equilibrium, tested by the constancy of p_{H} value of the clay suspension. The total amount of H^+ ions, exchanged for the cations, was determined by the KCl-KOH method using the clay system. In addition, the total amount of exchangeable ammonia, still present in the clay after exchange, was leached out and determined by nesslerisation and comparison of the colour produced by a standard solution of NH_4Cl . The amount of the other cation, *viz.*, Ba^{2+} and Na^+ , was then obtained by the difference (total m.e. originally present) - ($\text{M.e.H}^+ + \text{m.e.NH}_4^+$). The amounts of the two cations present in the binary systems and expressed as percentage of the total as well as of the respective cation of the mixed clay are shown in Tables I and II against the proportion of the two cations.

TABLE I

Types of clay.	Ratio $\text{NH}_4:\text{Ba}$.	% Ammonia released of the total		% Barium released of the total	
		exchangeable ions.	exchangeable ammonia.	exchangeable ions.	exchangeable Ba.
$\text{NH}_4\text{—Ba-clay}$ $\text{Ba—NH}_4\text{-clay}$ }	30:70	16.7	55.6	9.1	13.0
		5.2	17.3	16.0	22.9
$\text{NH}_4\text{—Ba-clay}$ $\text{Ba—NH}_4\text{-clay}$ }	50:50	20.0	40.0	4.5	9.0
		19.0	38.0	5.4	10.8
$\text{NH}_4\text{—Ba-clay}$ $\text{Ba—NH}_4\text{-clay}$ }	70:30	27.6	39.4	0.4	1.3
		23.4	33.4	0.4	1.3

TABLE II

Types of clay.	Ratio $\text{NH}_4:\text{Na}$.	% Ammonia released of the total		% Sodium released of the total.	
		exchangeable ions.	exchangeable NH_4 .	exchangeable ions.	exchangeable Na.
$\text{NH}_4\text{—Na-clay}$ $\text{Na—NH}_4\text{-clay}$ }	50:50	16.3	32.6	16.6	33.2
		2.9	5.8	24.5	49.0
$\text{NH}_4\text{—Na-clay}$ $\text{Na—NH}_4\text{-clay}$ }	70:30	11.5	16.4	15.9	53.0
		9.9	14.1	23.4	78.0

DISCUSSION

On comparing the $\text{NH}_4\text{—Ba-clay}$ and the $\text{Ba—NH}_4\text{-clay}$ having the same proportion of NH_4^+ and Ba^{2+} , it is found that NH_4^+ in the former is exchanged in a larger amount than in the latter. On the other hand, Ba^{2+} in the latter is more readily replaced by H^+ ions of H-resin than in the former. This general observation fails in the case of the mixed clays in which Ba^{2+} constitutes only 30%; this means that at or below 30%, Ba^{2+} is adsorbed in the same state of bonding in both the mixed clays. This is somewhat similar to the "critical ratio" observed earlier by Ganguly and Mukherjee

(*loc. cit.*), but the value of the ratio is less than that found for bivalent cations. In the case of Na—NH₄- and NH₄—Na-clays, the differentiation between the exchangeability of either Na⁺ or NH₄⁺ at the same porportion is similarly evident. It is also evident from the data that the same cation is not exchangeable to equal extents although present in the same porportion, showing that it is not adsorbed by the clay in identical manner ; perhaps the bonding energy is different.

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